

Lipid constituents of *Boerhaavia diffusa*

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Chemical studies of the root of *Boerhaavia diffusa* led to the isolation of four new compounds 5-methyleicos-4-ene (1), eicos-4-ene (2), 4-methyloctadec-3-ene (3) and 4-methylnonadecylbenzene (4).

Boerhaavia diffusa Linn. syn. *B. repens* Linn. is herbaceous member of the family Nyctaginaceae. This weed plant occurs throughout the plains and lower hills of India. It is the source of ayurvedic drug *punarnava*, the drug that rejuvenates¹. The roots are diuretic. Earlier work led to the isolation of punarnavoside², boerhaavinone A and B³, lignans⁴, hypoxanthin⁵ and flavonoids⁶. This paper describes the isolation of four new lipid constituents from the root of this plant.

Results and Discussion

Four compounds were isolated by silica gel chromatography of a *n*-hexane extract of *B. diffusa* roots.

Compound 1 (in traces, viscous mass) had IR bands at 1655 (double bond), 2930, 2860, 1460, 1380 and 720 cm^{-1} for unsaturated long chain hydrocarbon⁷. It had ¹H NMR signals at δ 5.33 (m) for a trisubstituted double bond proton and 1.56 (s) for methyl protons on double bond. It had $[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 294. Prominent ions, resulting from α - and β -cleavage to the double bond at m/z 211, 83, 251, 43 and 265, 197, 97, respectively, support the position of the double bond at C-4. The occurrence of a $[\text{M}-15]^+$ ion at m/z 279 suggested its branched chain nature⁸. Thus, 1 was assigned as 5-methyl-eicos-4-ene.

Compound 2 (in traces, viscous mass) had IR bands at 1650, 2920, 2860, 1460, 1380 and 720 cm^{-1} for a unsaturated straight chain hydrocarbon. Similar to 1, it had ¹H NMR signals at δ 5.33 (m) for a trisubstituted double bond proton but it lacks $[\text{M}-15]^+$ ion and at δ 1.56 which suggested no branching in the compound. Prominent ions at m/z 237, 211, 69, 43 and 251, 197, 83 are due to α - and β -cleavage to the double bond, respectively. Thus, compound 2 was characterized as eicos-4-ene.

Compound 3 (in traces, viscous mass) exhibited IR bands similar to 1 at 1640, 2920, 2850, 1470, 1380, 730 cm^{-1} for a long chain unsaturated hydrocarbon. It showed ¹H NMR

signals at δ 5.20 (m) for a trisubstituted double bond proton and 1.56 (s) for Me at double bond. The molecular ion appeared at m/z 266 and occurrence of $[\text{M}-15]^+$ suggested its branched chain nature. Prominent ions, resulting from α - and β -cleavage appeared at m/z 197, 69 and 183, 83, respectively, support the position of double bond at C-3. Therefore, the structure of compound 3 has been assigned as 4-methyloctadec-3-ene.

Compound 4 (in traces, viscous mass) had IR bands at 1600, 1580, 750, 730 cm^{-1} and ¹H NMR signals at δ 6.8–7.2 (m, 5H), suggesting it to be a singly substituted aromatic hydrocarbon⁹. It had $[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 358 ($\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{46}$) with the prominent peak at m/z 91, the tropylium ion formed by cleavage β to the aromatic ring¹⁰. The presence of a $[\text{M}-15]^+$ ion at m/z 343 and a doublet at δ 0.87 (3H) suggested the branched nature of the compound. A strong peak at m/z 71 favoured the branching at C-4. Thus, compound 4 was identified as 4-methylnonadecylbenzene.

Compound 5, obtained as needles, m.p. 122–124° was identified as sitosterol acetate by comparison with the authentic sample. Compound 6, obtained as needles, m.p. 130–132° was identified as sitosterol by comparison with authentic sample.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded. NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were measured (300 MHz) with TMS as int. standard. TLC was carried out on silica gel G and spots were visualized by exposure to I_2 vapor or after spraying with 50% H_2SO_4 solution. The homogeneity of compounds was checked on AgNO_3 -silica gel TLC in various solvent systems. Plant material was collected locally and a voucher specimen (No. 9261) was deposited in the herbarium of this Institute.

Dried and powdered root (2.0 kg) was extracted with ethanol, fractionated into *n*-hexane, CHCl_3 , *n*-BuOH and water-soluble fractions. The hexane extract (20 g) was

chromatographed over silica gel using varying percentage of hexane in ethyl acetate. Fractions (250 ml each) were collected and monitored by TLC.

5-Methyleicos-4-ene (1) : Frs. 3–6 of the hex : EtOAc (95 : 5) eluate was purified by preparative TLC to give compound 1 (10 mg); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2930, 2860, 1655, 1460, 1380, 770, 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.86 (6H, t, J 8 Hz), 1.26 (br s, $(\text{CH}_2)_n$), 1.56 (3H, s), 5.33 (1H, m); m/z (rel. int.) 294 $[\text{M}]^+$ (2.9), 279 $[\text{M-Me}]^+$ (3.0), 265 (3.6), 251 (3.4), 211 (3.3), 197 (3.0), 97 (12.4), 83 (22.2), 57 (51.2), 43 (100).

Eicos-4-ene (2) : Frs. 7–12 of the hex : EtOAc (95 : 5) eluate gave 2 (5 mg) after purification by preparative TLC; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2920, 2860, 1460, 1380, 770, 720 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.88 (6H, t J 8 Hz), 1.28 (br s, $(\text{CH}_2)_n$), 5.33 (1H, m); m/z (rel.int.) 280 $[\text{M}]^+$ (3.2), 251 (4.2), 237 (4.8), 211 (3.8), 197 (4.3), 83 (10.4), 69 (58.4), 57 (100), 43 (34.2).

4-Methylnonadecylbenzene (3) : Frs. 19–25 of the hex-EtOAc (95 : 5) eluate afforded 3 (10 mg) after purification by preparative TLC; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2920, 2845, 1600, 1580, 1520, 1460, 1380, 820, 750, 730 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.85 (3H, t, J 8 Hz), 0.87 (3H, d, J 8 Hz), 1.26 (br s, CH_2), 2.56 (2H, m), 6.8–7.2 (5H, m); m/z (rel. int.) 358 $[\text{M}]^+$ (1.4), 343 $[\text{M-Me}]^+$ (4.2), 329 (2.8), 315 (3.9), 287 (3.8), 147 (20.5), 133 (33.8), 105 (70.6), 91 (50.4), 85 (60.2), 71 (20.4), 43 (100).

4-Methyloctadec-3-ene (4) : Frs. 30–35 of the hex-EtOAc (95 : 5) eluate yielded 4 and purified by preparative TLC (5 mg); ν_{\max} 2920, 2850, 1640, 1470, 1380, 750, 730 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.86 (3H, t, J 8 Hz), 1.26 (br s, $(\text{CH}_2)_n$), 1.56 (3H, s), 5.20 (1H, m); m/z (rel. int.) 266 $[\text{M}]^+$ (4.2) 251

$[\text{M-Me}]^+$ (3.8), 237 (4.9), 197 (10.5), 183 (4.6), 97 (15.4), 83 (20.5), 57 (74.8), 43 (100).

Frs. 51–63 of hex-EtOAc (90 : 10) eluate yielded sitosterol acetate (5, 50 mg), confirmed by co-TLC, m.m.p. Frs. 189–304 of hex-EtOAc (70 : 30) eluate yielded sitosterol (6, 2 g), confirmed by co-TLC, m.m.p.

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